

**DESIGNING AN INDUCTOR FOR EDUCATIONAL PURPOSES:
MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PHYSICAL CONSTRUCTION**

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ABSTRACT

This work describes the development of an inductor for educational purposes, exploring its physical construction and providing a detailed mathematical analysis of its operation. The inductor is a key component in electrical circuits, responsible for storing energy in the form of a magnetic field, and its understanding is essential for the study of physics and electronics.

The physical construction of the inductor involved a careful selection of materials, such as the magnetic core and the conducting wire, and the application of precise winding techniques. The main objective was to create a functional device that could be used as a valuable didactic tool for teaching the principles of electromagnetic induction. In addition to the practical construction, a comprehensive mathematical analysis was carried out to understand the behavior of the inductor in different scenarios. Relevant equations related to electromagnetic induction were applied to calculate the inductance in different configurations. The theoretical results were compared with experimental data obtained through tests conducted with the built inductor. The integration of theory and practice proved to be essential for students' learning. Through the development and analysis of the inductor, the studies provided insight into how mathematical concepts apply in the real world, strengthening their understanding of electromagnetic phenomena. The study demonstrated the convergence of theoretical and practical results, validating the mathematical models used and reinforcing the accuracy of the measurements taken. This agreement between mathematical analysis and practical tests provided an enriching learning experience, stimulating students' interest and expanding their knowledge in physics and electronics. In summary, the development of this inductor for educational purposes, combined with detailed mathematical analysis, offers an effective approach to teach the principles of electromagnetic induction. Through this experience, students are empowered to comprehend the fundamental concepts of the field solidly and practically, consolidating their knowledge and preparing them for future challenges in the field of science and technology.

Keywords: Electromagnetism, Electric Machines, Engineering, Education.